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Student Information System

A Project report submitted to Visvesvaraya Technological University
in partial fulfillment of the award of degree of
Bachelor of Engineering in Electronics & Communication Engineering

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Certificate

This is to certify that the Project work entitled “**Student Information System**” is a bonafide work carried

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Abstract

An organized and systematic office solution is essential for all universities and organizations. There are many departments of administration for the maintenance of college information and student databases in any institution. All these departments provide various records. Most of these records maintain information about the students. Maintenance of the data manually kills time and man power. Hence there is need for the system to be automated and centralized.

In this context,a Student Information System is being designed which will track all the details of a student from the day one to the end of his course which can be used for all reporting purpose, progress in the course,to track attendance and broadcast IA marks and attendance percentage to the respective parents number.

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Introduction

Student Information System is an intelligent system which is used to maintain and manage the data regarding the students. These types of system can be implemented in various schools and colleges.

Student Information System deals with all kind of student details like

- Student Name
- USN
- Branch
- Semester
- Academic related reports (IA marks)
- Attendance percentage
- Parents and student mobile number
- Other related details

It tracks all the details of a student about his course which is used for all reporting purpose, progress in the course, current status of a student, tracking of attendance and upcoming requirements of a student regarding attendance.

Student Information system is managed by an administrator. It is the job of the administrator to insert, update and monitor the whole process. Admin has to go through the process of authentication in order to manage the database. The authentication is provided with the help of finger print scanner. The information regarding the IA marks and attendance are broadcasted to the respective parent's number through GSM.

In case of manual system they need a lot of time, manpower etc. Here almost all work is computerized. So the accuracy is maintained. Maintaining backup is also easy which can be done within a few minutes.

1.1 Problem Statement

The system has to maintain the database for all the users. Maintaining a database manually is quite a tedious job and the person can enter the details which may not be free from errors and also his speed and efficiency are not so reliable. Human based work takes a lot of unnecessary time and fails in real time logging of person's data. Person can use others details to get access and he may misuse their details.

1.2 Methodology

The complete idea of functionality of the student information system is to develop a platform to maintain student data, to provide capabilities for entering students test assessment scores, track students attendance, manage many other student related data needs and to broadcast the IA marks & Attendance percentage to the respective Parents number.

In SIS, various data of the student like USN no, Students name, Semester, Branch, Parents phone no., Students phone no., IA marks, Attendance percentage are maintained using Microsoft Visual Studio software. GUI is provided to enhance the interaction of the user with the Student database. Only Admin is given the provision to enter/update the student data. Biometric Scanner is used to provide authentication for the Admin's login. GSM is used to broadcast the student data (IA marks and Attendance percentage) to the respective parents phone no. UART Converter is used to interface GSM and Biometric Scanner to the PC.

C# programming language is used in our project because it is one amongst the first-class languages on the .NET platform. The language itself is stripped down to bare syntax, with all additional services moved into the .NET Framework Class Library, which is common to all languages.

Figure 1.1: Basic block diagram

1.3 Scope of the project

SIS provides the platform for maintaining the student's data in an efficient manner. These systems can be implemented in schools and colleges for tracking student's data. The scope of our project involves, broadcasting of student information i.e. IA marks and attendance percentage to the parents, so as to make the parents aware of their son's/daughter's academic performance.

1.4 Organization of the report

The flow of the project is as follows

- In chapter 2, the theoretical background of the terminology and details regarding DBMS are discussed.
- In chapter 3, the hardware used in the project is discussed.
- In chapter 4, the designing and implementation principle is discussed. The designing procedure for front end, table creation and maintenance are discussed.

- In chapter 5, the obtained results are discussed.
- In chapter 6, the references for project are reported. The various books, web sites and articles referred are mentioned.
- In chapter 7, the appendix of the project is reported. The codes used for the working of the project are presented and discussed.

Theoretical Background

In this chapter, the theoretical details of the Database Management System (DBMS) are discussed: how to maintain a database, details of SQL server, the software required for this purpose (Microsoft Visual Studio), creation of tables and front ends.

2.1 Database Management System (DBMS)

A database is a collection of related data. Data refers to the known facts that can be recorded and that have implicit meaning. A database is a logically coherent collection of data with some inherent meaning. A random assortment of data cannot correctly be referred to as a database. A database is designed, built and populated with data for specific purpose. It has intended group of users and some preconceived applications in which these users are interested. A database can be of any size and complexity. A database may be generated, maintained manually or it may be computerized [1].

A Database Management System (DBMS) is a collection of programs that enables users to create and maintain a database. The DBMS is a general purpose software system that facilitates the process of defining, constructing, manipulating and sharing databases among various users and applications.

- Defining a database involves specifying the data types, structures and constraints of data to be stored in the database.
- Constructing the database is the process of storing the data on some storage medium that is controlled by the DBMS.
- Manipulating a database includes functions such as querying the database to retrieve a specific data, updating the database to reflect changes and generating reports from the data.

- Sharing a database allow multiple users and programs to access data simultaneously.

Microsoft Visual Studio is used in our project to maintain the database using c#.net.Database projects include a SQL Server project type, offering close integration with SQL Server for building .NET code that runs inside of SQL Server. For example, we can write stored procedures and functions in either C# or other languages and have the benefit of the .NET Framework in our code. VS makes it easy to deploy the code to SQL Server with a single mouse click SQL Server stores each data item in its own fields. In SQL Server, the fields relating to a particular person, thing or event are bundled together to form a single complete unit of data, called a record (it can also be referred to as raw or an occurrence). Each record is made up of a number of fields. No two fields in a record can have the same field name.[2]

2.1.1 SQL Server

SQL Server stores records relating to each other in a table. Different tables are created for the various groups of information. Related tables are grouped together to form a database.

- **Primary Key:**

Every table in SQL Server has a field or a combination of fields that uniquely identifies each record in the table. The Unique identifier is called the Primary Key, or simply the Key. The primary key provides the means to distinguish one record from all the other in a table. It allows the user and the database system to identify, locate and refer to one particular record in the database.

- **Foreign Key:**

When a field in one table matches the primary key of another field, it is referred to as a foreign key. A foreign key is a field or a group of fields in one table whose values match those of the primary key of another table.

- **Referential Integrity:**

SQL Server not only allows one to link multiple tables, but it also maintains consistency between them. Ensures that the data among related tables is correctly matched which is referred to as referential integrity maintenance.

- **Relational Database:**

Sometimes all the information of interest to a business operation can be stored in one table. SQL Server makes it very easy to link the data in multiple tables. Matching an employee to the department in which they work is one example. This is what makes SQL Server a relational database management system, or RDBMS. It stores data in two or more tables and enables you to define relationships between the table and enables you to define relationships between the tables.

- **Data Abstraction:** A major purpose of a database system is to provide users an abstract view of the data. This system hides certain details of how the data is stored and maintained. Data abstraction is divided into three levels.

- Physical level: This is the lowest level of abstraction at which one describes how the data are actually stored.
- Conceptual Level: At this level of database abstraction all the attributed and stored data are described.
- View level: This is the highest level of abstraction at which one describes the database.

2.1.2 Advantages of RDBMS

- Redundancy can be avoided
- Inconsistency can be eliminated
- Data can be Shared
- Standards can be enforced
- Security restrictions ca be applied
- Integrity can be maintained
- Conflicting requirements can be balanced
- Data independence can be achieved.

2.1.3 Disadvantages of RDBMS

A significant disadvantage of the RDBMS system is cost. In addition to the cost of purchasing & developing the software, the hardware has to be upgraded so as to support the extensive programs and the workspace required for their execution and storage. While centralization reduces duplication, the lack of duplication requires that the database to be adequately backed up so that in case of failure the data can be recovered.

2.2 Microsoft Visual Studio 2010

Visual Studio 2010 (VS) is an integrated development environment (IDE); a set of tools in a single application that helps you write programs. Without VS, we would need to open a text editor, write all of the code, and then run a command-line compiler to create an executable application. The issue with the text editor and command-line compiler is that you would lose a lot of productivity through manual processes [3] .

Whenever we start a new project, VS will automatically generate a skeleton code that can compile and run immediately. Each project type has a project item which includes skeleton code. The VS editor optimizes the coding experience. Much of the code is colorized, Intellisense; tips that pop up as one types, keyboard shortcuts for performing a multitude of tasks, Re-factoring; features to quickly improve the organization of the code.

VS contains Toolbox jam-packed with controls, a Server Explorer for working with operating system services and databases, a Solution Explorer for working with the projects, testing utilities, and visual designers. We can customize many parts of the VS environment, including colors, editor options, and layout. The rich and customizable development environment in VS helps us work the way we want to.

2.2.1 Installing Visual Studio 2010

The Microsoft Visual Studio 2010 window appears [4] as shown in figure 2.1 .

- Click Install Microsoft Visual Studio 2010.

Figure 2.1: Microsoft Visual Studio 2010 Setup window

- During the installation process following VS components is successfully installed as shown in figure 2.2

Figure 2.2: Setup Progress window

- The choice made for default environment settings depends on the language or environment used to write the software. choose the default environment setting as

”Visual C# development setting” as shown in figure 2.3

Figure 2.3: Default Environment Settings window

2.2.2 Visual Studio 2010 Environment

- **Menu bar:** The menu bar is the standard part of most windows applications. Menu bar includes ”File,” ”Edit,” ”View,” ”Tools,” and so on. The File menu is where we can create new projects. The File menu also gives access to recently opened files and projects. The Edit menu has standard cut, copy, and paste operations. It also gives access to a bookmark feature for providing easy navigation through source code. The View menu gives access to all of the tool windows in VS . The View menu also has a menu item named Other Windows that includes more application windows that will come in handy as new software is created [5] .

The Tools menu contains debugger to see other programs run, line by line, connect to a database for data and more. An important menu item on the Tools menu is Options, which exposes hundreds of settings for customizing the VS environment. The Test menu finds all of the functionality for performing unit tests to test new software one part at a time. The Analyze, Architecture, and Team menus have advanced functionality for improving the performance of an application, working with application architecture, and integrating with Microsoft’s Team Foundation Server.

The Windows and Help menus are similar to most other application types, where the Windows menu allows us to manipulate the VS windows and the Help menu gives technical documentation on VS. The toolbar contains frequently accessed functionality that is a subset of what is available via menus. The toolbars are context-sensitive, showing and hiding depending on what is being done on VS. The toolbar customization window allows to add any features to the current toolbar.

- **Work Area:**

Work Area is used to write code and work with visual designers. The Start page is divided into two sections: project management and information. The project management side of the page, on the left, offers a quick way to start new projects or work with a list of recently opened projects. The information side of the page, on the right, contains resources to get started with VS, such as links to the Microsoft Web site, walk through to help learn new features, and a tab that updates with the latest developer news from Microsoft.

- **Toolbox:**

Toolbox is a vertical tab that contains a context sensitive list of controls that can be dragged and dropped onto the current designer surface.

- **Solution Explorer:**

The Solution Explorer window, is where solutions, projects, and project items will appear. Here we can organize all of the files and settings that belong to a project.

- **Status Bar:**

The Status bar communicates what is happening with VS at the current time. If the Status bar displays the word "Ready" we can begin to use VS at any time.

2.3 Design Procedure

The various procedures for the design of tables and front-ends are discussed in this section

2.3.1 Creation of Database

The tables are used to store the user data. Inside the table we can add any number of variables of different data types depending on our requirement. Various data types can be numeric, char, nvarchar etc. Once the tables are created, the table contents can be entered or modified by pressing "SHOW TABLE DATA". Figure 2.4 shows the sample table which contains the user database.

Column Name	Data Type	Allow Nulls
iao	nvarchar(20)	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
sub1	nvarchar(20)	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
sub2	nvarchar(20)	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
sub3	nvarchar(20)	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
sub4	nvarchar(20)	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
sub5	nvarchar(20)	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
sub6	nvarchar(20)	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
pcell	nvarchar(20)	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
scell	nvarchar(20)	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>

Figure 2.4: Database

2.3.2 Front-End Design

1. Point to the lower-right corner of the form until the mouse pointer changes to a resizing pointer, and then drag to increase the size of the form.

Figure 2.5: Sample form

2. Click the Toolbox tab to display the Toolbox window in the IDE or select View > Toolbox from the menu (or type Ctrl+Alt+X). The Toolbox contains all the controls used to build Visual Basic programs as shown in figure 2.6.

Figure 2.6: Contents of Toolbox

3. To create a button, Double-click the Button control in the Toolbox, and then move the mouse pointer away from the Toolbox. The button is named Button1 because it is the first button in the program. We can enlarge the button by dragging the pointer down and to the right.
4. To create a Label, Double-click the Label control in the Toolbox. Visual Studio creates a label object on the form. The label object is just large enough to hold the text contained in the object, but it can be resized. Figure 2.7 shows a sample of a form containing button and labels.

Figure 2.7: Adding button and label to the form

5. To change the properties

- Select the components whose properties need to be changed.
- Click the Properties window title bar or press F4.
- At the top of the Properties window, click the Categorized button. Properties window looks as in figure 2.8

Figure 2.8: Properties

- The Properties window includes settings for the background color, text, font height, and width of the button etc.
- To edit the text, Double-click the Text property in the first column of the Properties window. Type the text and then press ENTER.

6. Also Combo boxes can be created in the same fashion. The various options that need to be shown by combo box are listed in the property window.

2.4 Bare-Bones Project

To get started, open VS and select File -> New -> Project. We will see the New Project window, shown in Figure 2.9 .The Console Application should be selected as the program type .NET Framework is the set of class libraries, runtime, and languages that is the development platform supported by VS. VS allows one to target multiple versions of the .NET Framework,including versions 2.0, 3.0, 3.5, and 4.0. VS will compile the code against the version choosed. Generally, all new projects are done with the latest version, 4.0,

Having run the New Project Wizard for a Console application, next we see a file named Program.cs (or Module.vb) that contains skeleton code in the editor. VS will create skeleton code using built-in templates for most project types that we create. We are allowed to add, remove, or modify this code as needed. Console application skeleton code contains the following libraries.[6]

```
using System;  
using System.Collections.Generic;  
using System.Linq;  
using System.Text;
```


Figure 2.9: Console

2.5 Summary

Finally complete information about DBMS, Microsoft Visual Studio, SQL server, creation of tables and forms has been provided in this chapter. This enables one to work with Microsoft Visual Studio and to create database tables and user interface only.

Hardware Details

In the previous chapter, a detail information about DBMS is provided. Moving a step ahead, let us discuss about the various hardware components used in this project which are GSM: to broadcast the messages (IA and attendance percentage), Fingerprint module: to provide authentication for admin, RS232 and MAX232: for TTL compatibility.

3.1 GSM

A GSM network is composed of several functional entities, whose functions and interfaces are specified. Figure 3.1 shows the layout of a generic GSM network. GSM network can be divided into 3 broad parts. The Mobile station is carried by the subscriber. The base subsystem controls the radio link with the mobile services switching center (MSC), performs the switching of calls between the mobile users and between mobile and fixed network users. The MSC also handles the mobility management operation. Not shown is the operation maintenance center, which oversees the proper operation and setup of the network. The Mobile station and the Base station subsystem communicate across the Um interface, also known as the air interface or radio link. The Base station subsystem communicate with the Mobile service switching center across the A interface.

3.1.1 GSM modem - SIM 300

A GSM modem is a wireless modem that works with GSM wireless network. A wireless mode behaves like dial up modem. The main difference between them is that a dial up modem sends and receives data through a fixed telephone line while a wireless modem sends and receives through radio waves.

Figure 3.1: GSM generic architecture

- **SIM 300 Characteristics:**

- Tri band GSM GPRS modem (SIM 300 V7.03)
- Designed for GPRS, Fax, SMS and voice application
- Fully compatible with ETSI GSM phase 2 + specifications (normal mobile station)
- Input voltage 8V- 40V
- Input current: 8mA in idle mode , 150mA in communication GSM 900 12V
- Temperature range: Operating -20 to +55 degree Celsius, storage -25 to +70 degree Celsius
- Supply voltage range: 3.4v - 4.5V
- Dimension: 40*33*5.5mm
- Control via AT commands

- **Description:**

Designed for global market. SIM 300 is a Tri-band GSM/ GPRS engine that works on frequencies EGSM 900 MHz , DCS 100 MHz and PCS 1900 MHz. SIM 300 provides GPRS multi-slot class 10 capability and support the GPRS coding schemes CS-1, CS-2, CS-3 and CS-4. The SIM 300 is designed with power saving techniques, current consumption to as low as 2.5mA in SLEEP mode. The SIM 300 is integrated

with the TCP/ IP protocol, extended TCP/ IP AT commands are developed for customer to use the TCP/ IP protocol easily, which is very useful for these data transfer applications.

- **SIM card applications:**

We can use AT commands to get information in SIM card. The SIM interface supports the functionality of the GSM phase 1 specification and also supports the functionality of new GSM phase2 + specification for FAST 64kbps SIM. Both 1.8V and 3.0V SIM cards are supported. The SIM interface is powered from an internal regulator in the module having nominal voltage 2.8v.

- **Working state of network status indication LED pin**

The pin 30 on the board to board connector can be used to drive a network status indication lamp. The working state of pins is listed in the following table.

Table 3.1: Working status of pins

STATE	SIM 300 FUNCTION
Off	SIM 300 is not running
64ms on /800ms off	SIM300 does not find the network
64ms on /3000ms off	SIM 300 find the network
64ms on /300ms off	GPRS communication

- **Configuring SIM300**

SIM300 is configured using AT commands by setting the communication baud rate as 9600 in Hyper terminal software between the PC terminal and GSM modem. The various commands AT (Attention) commands used to command the GSM module are as shown below

AT+CMGS // Send message

AT+CMGF=1// set the message mode to normal texting mode

AT+CMGW// write message to memory

AT+CPIN//Check for SIM insertion

AT+CREG//Network registration

The SIM 300 has 64kb memory and can store up to 26 messages. These memory locations are used to store the messages required to send to the user mobile.

3.2 FINGERPRINT SCANNER

Fingerprint processing includes two parts: fingerprint enrollment and fingerprint matching (the matching can be 1:1 or 1:N). When enrolling, user needs to enter the finger on optical sensor . The system will process the finger images, generate a template of the finger based on processing results and store the template. When matching, user enters the finger through optical sensor and system will generate a template of the finger and compare it with templates of the finger library. For 1:1 matching, system will compare the live finger with specific template designated in the Module; for 1:N matching, or searching, system will search the whole finger library for the matching finger. In both circumstances, system will return the matching result, success or failure.

Figure 3.2: Fingerprint module

3.2.1 Physical parameters

Table 3.2: Physical parameters

Power	DC 3.6V-6.0V	Interface	UART(TTL logical level) /USB 1.1
Working current	Typical: 100mA Peak: 150mA	Matching Mode	1:1 and 1:N
Baud rate	(9600*N)bps, N=1 12(default N=6)	Character file size	256 bytes
Image acquiring time	<0.5s	Template size	512 bytes
Storage capacity	120/ 375/ 880	Security level	5 (1, 2, 3, 4, 5(highest))
FAR	<0.001%	FRR	<0.1%
Average searching time	<0.8s (1:880)	Window dimension	18mm*22mm
Working environment	Temp: -10- +40 RH:40p-85%	Storage environment	Temp: -40- +85 RH<85%

3.2.2 System Resources

Module system provides abundant resources at users use.

- **Buffer:**

There are an image buffer and two 512-byte-character-file buffer within the RAM space of the module. Users can read & write any of the buffers by instructions.

- **Image buffer:**

ImageBuffer serves for image storage and the image format is 256*288 pixels. When transferring through UART, to quicken speed, only the upper 4 bits of the pixel is transferred (that is 16 grey degrees). And two adjacent pixels of the same row will form a byte before the transferring. When uploaded to PC, the 16-grey-degree image will be extended to 256-grey-degree format. Thats 8-bit BMP format. When transferring through USB, the image is 8-bit pixel, thats 256 grey degrees.

- **Character file buffer:**

Character file buffer, CharBuffer1, CharBuffer2, can be used to store both character file and template file.

Fingerprint Library

System sets aside a certain space within Flash for fingerprint template storage, that's fingerprint library. Contents of the library remain at power off. Capacity of the library changes with the capacity of Flash, system will recognize the latter automatically. Fingerprint templates storage in Flash is in sequential order. Assume the fingerprint capacity N, then the serial number of template in library is 0, 1, 2, 3 N. User can only access library by template number.

3.2.3 System Configuration Parameter

To facilitate users developing, Module opens part system parameters for use. And the basic instructions are SetSysPara & ReadSysPara. Both instructions take Parameter Number as parameter. When upper computer sends command to modify parameter, Module first responses with original configurations, then performs the parameter modification and writes configuration record into Flash. At the next startup, system will run with the new configurations.

- Baud rate control

The Parameter controls the UART communication speed of the Module. Its value is an integer N, $N = [1, 12]$. Corresponding baud rate is $9600 * N$ bps.

- Security Level

The Parameter controls the matching threshold value of fingerprint searching and matching. Security level is divided into 5 grades, and corresponding value is 1, 2, 3, 4, 5. At level 1, FAR is the highest and FRR is the lowest; however at level 5, FAR is the lowest and FRR is the highest.

- Data package length

The parameter decides the max length of the transferring data package when communicating with upper computer. Its value is 0, 1, 2, 3, corresponding to 32 bytes, 64 bytes, 128 bytes, 256 bytes respectively.

System status register

System status register indicates the current operation status of the Module. Its length is 1 word, and can be read via instruction ReadSysPara. Definition of the register is as follows: Bit Num 15 4 3 2 1 0 Description Reserved ImgBufStat PWD Pass Busy Note: Busy:1 bit. 1: system is executing commands; 0: system is free; Pass:1 bit. 1: find the matching finger; 0: wrong finger; PWD:1 bit. 1: Verified devices handshaking password. ImgBufStat:1 bit. 1: image buffer contains valid image.

3.3 UART converter

- RS232: RS232 is a standard for serial communication transmission of data. It formally defines the signals connecting between DTE(data terminal equipment) such as computer terminal, and a DCE(data circuit-terminating equipment), originally defined as data communication equipment.

Figure 3.3: RS232 female socket and male socket

Pin	Signal	Direction	Description
1	DCD	DTE (- DCE)	Data Carrier Detect (when connected).
2	RxD	DTE (- DCE)	Received Data (sent from DCE).
3	TxD	DTE (-> DCE)	Transmitted Data (sent from DTE).
4	DTR	DTE (-> DCE)	Data Terminal Ready (for connection).
5	GND		Common ground.
6	DSR	DTE (- DCE)	Data Set Ready (to connect).
7	RTS	DTE (-> DCE)	Request To Send (or DTE ready to receive).
8	CTS	DTE (- DCE)	Clear To Send (or DCE ready to receive).
9	RI	DTE (- DCE)	Ring Indicator (with incoming call).

Figure 3.4: TTL table for RS232

- MAX232:

The MAX232 is an IC that converts signals from an RS232 serial port to signals suitable for using TTL compatible digital logic circuit.

RS232 line type and logic level	RS232 voltage	TTL voltage to/from MAX232
Data transmission (Rx/Tx) logic 0	+3 V to +15 V	0 V
Data transmission (Rx/Tx) logic 1	-3 V to -15 V	5 V
Control signals (RTS/CTS/DTR/DSR) logic 0	-3 V to -15 V	5 V
Control signals (RTS/CTS/DTR/DSR) logic 1	+3 V to +15 V	0 V

Figure 3.5: TTL table for MAX232

3.4 Summary

The complete information about GSM interfacing:AT commands,working of Fingerprint scanner and TTL compatable UART are provided in this chapter.With these prior knowledge of software and the various hardware specifications,it enables one to interface these hardware with the database so as to build a real time application.

Design and Implementation

This chapter presents the design and implementation aspects of the proposed work. The various informations about MVS and hardware given in previous chapters helps us to design the required front-end and tables which are used in our project.

4.1 Implementation flow diagram

Figure 4.1 shows the overview of proposed project. It gives the complete idea of functionality of SIS. The flowchart indicates the various steps involved in SIS

1. Student Information system is managed by an administrator.
2. Admin has to go through the process of authentication in order to manage the database. Authentication is provided by the finger print scanner.
3. Only the authorized user will be allowed to proceed further, otherwise an error message saying "Invalid User" is displayed on the console.
4. Once the Admin logs in, he can insert, update and monitor the database.
5. Later the data is broadcasted through GSM.

Figure 4.1: Basic software design

The detailed steps involved in each process are represented by the following flowcharts.

- Biometric scanner: To check whether the admin is valid user or not. This authentication procedure is depicted by figure 4.2
- The steps involved in broadcast of IA marks are depicted in figure 4.3
- The steps involved in broadcast of attendance percentage are depicted in figure 4.4
- GSM initialization process involves the following steps which are represented from figure 4.5 to 4.9

Flowchart for ;

- To check whether the port is open or not
- SIM check; to check whether the SIM is inserted properly
- SMS text mode; to set SMS to text mode using the command `AT+CMGF = 1`
- SIM registration
- Delete the messages from GSM buffer

Figure 4.2: Biometric authentication

Figure 4.3: Broadcasting of IA

Figure 4.4: Broadcasting attendance percentage

Flowchart of GSM initialization

Figure 4.5: SMS port open

Figure 4.6: SMS check

Figure 4.7: SMS text mode

Figure 4.8: SIM registration

Figure 4.9: Clearing GSM buffer

4.2 Database Management

For the ease of accessing, the database of the students are maintained in 3 different tables.

- Table 1 contains USN, student's name, branch, semester, parent's and student's mobile number as represented by figure 4.10
- Table 2 contains USN, IA number, marks obtained in each subject (sub1 to sub6), parent's and student's mobile number as represented by figure 4.11
- Table 3 contains USN, report number, attendance percentage of 6 subjects as represented by figure 4.12

Figure 4.10: Student Information Table

Figure 4.11: IA data table

id	iano	usn	pcell	scell	nclass1	nat1	nper1	nclass2	nat2	nper2
1	first	4n11ec019	012378964	99195239	20	20	100	20	20	100
3	FIRST	4N11EC009	012378964	701910570	20	20	100	20	10	50
2	FIRST	4N11EC040	916461079		20	20	100	20	20	100
NULL	NULL	NULL	NULL	NULL	NULL	NULL	NULL	NULL	NULL	NULL

Figure 4.12: Attendance data table

4.3 Front-End Design

Front end is used to provide user interface. This is user friendly allowing the user having less knowledge of the software to interact with the database.[7] Different front ends used in our project are listed below

- An authentication form is created for the purpose of log-in as shown in figure 4.13
- Forms are designed for student entry, IA entry and Attendance percentage entry.
 - FORM: "Student Information System" - This is main IS form which contains six buttons from button1 to button6 for Student Entry, IA Entry, Attendance Entry, IA SMS, Att SMS, Close respectively.
 - FORM: "Student Entry"- It provides the facility for entering different student data like USN, Name, Dept., Semester, parent's and student mobile number into Table 1 i.e., Student Information Table.
 - FORM: "IA Entry"- It provides the facility for entering IA marks of 6 subjects into Table 2 i.e., IA data Table.
 - FORM: "ATT Entry"- It provides the facility for entering attendance percentage of 6 subjects into Table 3 i.e., Attendance data Table. The respective forms are

shown from figure 4.14 to 4.17

- Forms are designed to send the SMS containing IA marks of different tests and respective Attendance percentage as shown in Figure 4.18 and 4.19 .

Here provision is given to generate the reports of respective tests by using GENERATE (Button) and REPORT/ SELECT IA (Combo Box).

The generated reports are sent to the respective parent's mobile number using GO SMS (Button).

Refer Appendix for codes that are used to create the above forms.

Figure 4.13: Login Form

Figure 4.14: Main SIS Form

Figure 4.15: Student Entry Form

STUDENT INFORMATION SYSTEM

IA Marks entry

IA NO:

Subject 1: Subject 2:

Subject 3: Subject 4:

Subject 5: Subject 6:

USN	NAME	BRANCH	SEMESTER
4JN11EC009	Ashwini T G	ELECTRONICS	VIII SEM
4jn11ec009	Ashwini T G	ELECTRONICS	VIII SEM

Figure 4.16: IA Entry Form

Form6

REPORT:

SUBJECTS NO. CLASSES ASS PERCENTAGE

Subject 1:

Subject 2:

Subject 3:

Subject 4:

Subject 5:

Subject 6:

USN	NAME	BRANCH	SEMESTER
4JN11EC009	Ashwini T G	ELECTRONICS	VIII SEM
4jn11ec009	Ashwini T G	ELECTRONICS	VIII SEM

Figure 4.17: Attendance Form

The screenshot shows a window titled "STUDENT INFORMATION SYSTEM" containing a sub-window titled "IA SMS". The sub-window features a table with the following columns: USN, IA NO, SUB1, SUB2, SUB3, SUB4, SUB5, SUB6, and CELL NUMBER. To the right of the table, there is a "Select IA" dropdown menu with options "FIRST", "SECOND", and "THIRD". Below it is a "Select Port" dropdown menu. At the bottom right, there are three buttons: "GENERATE", "GO SMS", and "CLOSE".

Figure 4.18: IA SMS Form

The screenshot shows a window titled "STUDENT INFORMATION SYSTEM" containing a sub-window titled "ATTENDANCE SMS". The sub-window features a table with the following columns: USN, NUMBER, SUB1 PERCENTAGE, SUB2 PERCENTAGE, SUB3 PERCENTAGE, SUB4 PERCENTAGE, SUB5 PERCENTAGE, PARENT CELL NO, and STATUS. Above the table, there is a "SELECT NO:" dropdown menu and a "GENERATE" button. To the right of the table, there is a "Select Port" dropdown menu with options "COM1", "COM2", "COM3", "COM4", "COM5", "COM6", "COM7", "COM8", "COM9", "COM10", "COM11", "COM12", "COM13", "COM14", "COM15", "COM16", "COM17", "COM18", "COM19", and "COM20". At the bottom right, there is a "GO SMS" button.

Figure 4.19: Attendance SMS Form

Results and Discussion

Student Information System provides an efficient software for managing students data. Manual systems need lot of time, manpower etc where as SIS consumes less time, at the same time provides more accuracy and easy backup of data. The proposed system allows only the authorized user to access the system which makes the system more secured. Figure 5.1 shows the SIS setup.

Figure 5.1: SIS setup

Here IA marks of different internals are stored in the database but provision is given to broadcast marks of only the respective internal. In the similar way attendance of all subjects are stored. Provision is given to calculate the attendance percentage automatically just by entering the total number of classes and number of classes attended and the same is broadcasted to parent's mobile number. Student having attendance less than 75% will be warned by a "SHORTAGE" message.

The format of the broadcasted messages is shown in the figure 5.2.

Figure 5.2: SMS format of IA and attendance percentage

Finally the Student Information System is tested under working environment and the results are obtained successfully. Thus this system is now ready to be implemented in colleges and schools.

Conclusion and Future Scope

SIS is an intelligent system which is used to maintain and manage the data regarding student. Maintaining these data manually is quite tedious, consumes more time and there may be chances of entering erroneous information. But SIS consumes less time and provides an efficient solution for the above problems.

In our project IA marks and attendance percentage of all internals are stored in the database and the same is broadcasted to the respective parent's mobile number. Also, those students having attendance less than 75% are warned by a "SHORTAGE" message. Only the authorized users can access the system which makes the system more secure.

Presently the system has been designed to maintain the data of final year EC students and tested in working conditions. Fingerprints of 9 users has been enrolled and tested for authentication.

The application of SIS is that it can be implemented in schools and colleges for tracking and maintain the student's academic details. The future scope of our project involves,a facility to the student to access the information by sending a request message. Project can be further extended to provide a provision for fee payment and maintaining the database regarding the books available in the library.

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.NET Codes

.NET programs are used throughout the the SIS for . Source code of important programs is attached here. The codes are arranged chapter wise.

A.1 Form5:Code for Login Form

```
using System;
using System.Collections.Generic;
using System.ComponentModel;
using System.Data;
using System.Drawing;
using System.Linq;
using System.Text;
using System.Windows.Forms;
using System.IO;
using System.IO.Ports;
using System.Threading;

namespace studentinfo
{
    public partial class Form8 : Form
    {
        SerialPort port;
        string sql;
        string l1, l2, l3, l4, l5, l6, l7, l8, l9;

        public Form8()
        {
            InitializeComponent();
        }

        private void button1_Click(object sender, EventArgs e)
        {
            port.Close();
            port.Open();
        }
    }
}
```

```
port.Write(new byte[] { 0xEF, 0x01, 0xFF, 0xFF,
    0xFF, 0xFF, 0x01, 0x00, 0x03, 0x01, 0x00, 0x05},
    0, 12);

Thread.Sleep(1500);
int v1 = port.ReadChar();
// MessageBox.Show(v1.ToString());
if (v1 == 0)
{
    MessageBox.Show("Finger print sucess");
}
else
{
    if (v1 == 2)
    {
        MessageBox.Show("Cannot detect Finger ");
    }
    else
    {
        MessageBox.Show("Error");
    }
}

Thread.Sleep(1500);
port.Close();
port.Open();
// step 2 character array

port.Write(new byte[] { 0xEF, 0x01, 0xFF, 0xFF,
    0xFF, 0xFF, 0x01, 0x00, 0x04, 0x02, 0x01, 0x00,0x08},
    0, 13);

int v2 = port.ReadChar();
```

```
v2 = port.ReadChar();
v2 = port.ReadChar();
//v2 = port.ReadChar();
// MessageBox.Show(v2.ToString() + "Please click to continue");

// step3 scan
Thread.Sleep(1500);
port.Close();
port.Open();
port.Write(new byte[] { 0xEF, 0x01, 0xFF, 0xFF,
    0xFF, 0xFF, 0x01, 0x00, 0x03, 0x01, 0x00, 0x05},
    0, 12);

// port.Write(new byte[] { 0x0A }, 0, 1);
Thread.Sleep(1500);
// string v;
v1 = port.ReadChar();
//v1 = port.ReadChar();
//v1 = port.ReadChar();
// v=port.ReadExisting().ToString();
// Int64 bb = Convert.ToInt64(v);
// string hexOutput = String.Format("{0:X}", v1);

//MessageBox.Show(v1.ToString());

//step 4 charcter array
Thread.Sleep(1500);
port.Close();
port.Open();
// step 4 charctrer array

port.Write(new byte[] { 0xEF, 0x01, 0xFF, 0xFF,
    0xFF, 0xFF, 0x01, 0x00, 0x04, 0x02, 0x02, 0x00,0x09},
    0, 13);

v2 = port.ReadChar();
```

```
v2 = port.ReadChar();
//v2 = port.ReadChar();
// MessageBox.Show(v2.ToString() + "Please click to continue");
Thread.Sleep(1500);

//step 5 template gen
port.Close();
port.Open();
// step 2 character array

port.Write(new byte[] { 0xEF, 0x01, 0xFF, 0xFF,
    0xFF, 0xFF, 0x01, 0x00, 0x03, 0x05, 0x00, 0x09},
    0, 12);

v2 = port.ReadChar();

// step 3
port.Close();
port.Open();
int v6;
port.Write(new byte[] { 0xEF, 0x01, 0xFF, 0xFF,
    0xFF, 0xFF, 0x01, 0x00, 0x08, 0x04, 0x01, 0x00, 0x01, 0x00, 0x09},
    0, 17);

// port.Write(new byte[] { 0x0A }, 0, 1);
Thread.Sleep(1500);
// string v;
v1 = port.ReadChar();
```

```
v1 = port.ReadChar();
v1 = port.ReadChar();
v6 = port.ReadChar();
v6 = port.ReadChar();

if (v1 == 0)
{
    if (v6 == 1)
    {
        label4.Text = 11 + " SUCCESFULLY LOGGED WITH DATE: " +
        // sql = "insert into tbl_staff values('" + v6.ToString()
        // sql="insert into tbl_staff values('1','xcvcxv','vxcvx
        button2.Enabled = true;
    }
    if (v6 == 2)
    {
        label4.Text = 12 + "SUCCESFULLY LOGGED WITH DATE: " +
        //sql = "insert into tbl_staff values('" + v6.ToString()
        button2.Enabled = true;
    }
    if (v6 == 3)
    {
        label4.Text = 13 + "SUCCESFULLY LOGGED WITH DATE: " +
        // sql = "insert into tbl_staff values('" + v6.ToString()
        button2.Enabled = true;
    }
    if (v6 == 4)
    {
        label4.Text = 14 + "SUCCESFULLY LOGGED WITH DATE: " +
        //sql = "insert into tbl_staff values('" + v6.ToString()
        button2.Enabled = true;
    }
    if (v6 == 5)
    {
        label4.Text = 15 + "SUCCESFULLY LOGGED WITH DATE: " +
        //sql = "insert into tbl_staff values('" + v6.ToString()
        button2.Enabled = true;
    }
    if (v6 == 6)
    {
        label4.Text = 16 + "SUCCESFULLY LOGGED WITH DATE: " +
        //
        sql = "insert into tbl_staff values('" + v6.ToString()
        button2.Enabled = true;
    }
    if (v6 == 7)
    {
        label4.Text = 17 + "SUCCESFULLY LOGGED WITH DATE: " +
        //
        sql = "insert into tbl_staff values('" + v6.ToString()
        button2.Enabled = true;
    }
}
```

```
        if (v6 == 8)
        {
            label4.Text = 18 + " SUCCESFULLY LOGGED WITH DATE: " +
//            sql = "insert into tbl_staff values('" + v6.ToString()
            button2.Enabled = true;
        }
        if (v6 == 9)
        {
            label4.Text = 19 + "SUCCESFULLY LOGGED WITH DATE: " +
//            sql = "insert into tbl_staff values('" + v6.ToString()
            button2.Enabled = true;
        }
    }
    else
    {
        label4.Text = " You are invalid user";
        button2.Enabled = false;
    }
}

private void Form8_Load(object sender, EventArgs e)
{
    button2.Enabled = false;
    port = new SerialPort("COM15");
    l1 = "ASHWINI";
    l2 = "VARSHA";
    l3 = "AKSHATHA";
    l4 = "SHANTHALA";
    l5 = "LAVANYA";
    l6 = "USHA";
    l7 = "ANJUM";
    l8 = "RANJITHA";
    l9 = "DEEKSHA";
}

private void button2_Click(object sender, EventArgs e)
{
    button2.Enabled = false;
    Form win = new Form1();
    win.Show();
}

private void label2_Click(object sender, EventArgs e)
{
}

private void label3_Click(object sender, EventArgs e)
{
}
```

```
    }  
  }  
}
```

A.2 Form1:Code for SIS Main Form

```
using System;  
using System.Collections.Generic;  
using System.ComponentModel;  
using System.Data;  
using System.Drawing;  
using System.Linq;  
using System.Text;  
using System.Windows.Forms;  
  
namespace studentinfo  
{  
  public partial class Form1 : Form  
  {  
    public Form1()  
    {  
      InitializeComponent();  
    }  
  
    private void Form1_Load(object sender, EventArgs e) //to display the form1 i.  
    {  
  
    }  
  
    private void button4_Click(object sender, EventArgs e) //button4 is defined a  
  
    this.Close();  
  }  
  
  private void button1_Click(object sender, EventArgs e) //button1 i.e., STUDEN  
  {  
  
    Form bb = new Form2();  
    bb.Show();  
  }  
  
  private void button2_Click(object sender, EventArgs e) //button2 i.e., IA ENT  
  {
```

```
Form bb2 = new Form3();
bb2.Show();
MessageBox.Show("Select the appropriate USN to proceed.....");
}

private void button3_Click(object sender, EventArgs e) //button3 i.e., IA SMS
{
Form BB3 = new Form4();
BB3.Show();
}

private void button5_Click(object sender, EventArgs e) //button5 i.e., Attend
{
Form bb4 = new Form6();
bb4.Show();
MessageBox.Show("Select the appropriate USN to proceed.....");
}

private void button6_Click(object sender, EventArgs e) //button3 i.e., Attend
{
Form bb5 = new Form7();
bb5.Show();
}
}
}
```

A.3 Form2:Code for Student Entry Form

```
using System;
using System.Collections.Generic;
using System.ComponentModel;
using System.Data;
using System.Drawing;
using System.Linq;
using System.Text;
using System.Windows.Forms;
using System.Data.SqlClient;
namespace studentinfo
{
public partial class Form2 : Form
{
SqlConnection con;
SqlCommand com;
public Form2()
}
```

```
{
    InitializeComponent();
}

private void Form2_Load(object sender, EventArgs e) //loads the form2
{
    button1.Enabled = true; //button1= ADD
    button2.Enabled = false; //button2= SAVE
}
private void dbconnect()
{
    con=new SqlConnection("Data Source=.\SQLEXPRESS;
AttachDbFilename=c:\\studentinfo\\database\\sis.mdf;Integrated
con.Open();

}
private void button1_Click(object sender, EventArgs e)
{
    txtclr();
    button1.Enabled = false;
    button2.Enabled = true;
}
private void txtclr()
{
    textBox1.Clear();// textbox1=ENTER USN
    textBox2.Clear();// textbox2= ENTER NAME
    textBox9.Clear();//textbox9= PARENT CELL NO
    textBox10.Clear();// textbox10= STUDENT CELL NO
    comboBox1.Text = ""; // to select the department
    comboBox2.Text = ""; //to select the semester
}

private void button2_Click(object sender, EventArgs e)
{
    button2.Enabled = false;
    button1.Enabled = true;
    try
    {
        dbconnect();
        string sql;
        sql = "insert into tbl_student values('" + textBox1.Text + "'";
        com = new SqlCommand(sql, con);
        com.ExecuteNonQuery();
        MessageBox.Show("Record saved");
        con.Close();
    }
    catch (Exception e1)
    {
        MessageBox.Show(e1.ToString());
    }
}
```

```
    }

    private void button3_Click(object sender, EventArgs e)%button3= CLOSE
    {
        this.Hide();
    }
}
}
```

A.4 Form3:Code for IA Entry Form

```
using System;
using System.Collections.Generic;
using System.ComponentModel;
using System.Data;
using System.Drawing;
using System.Linq;
using System.Text;
using System.Windows.Forms;
using System.Data.SqlClient;
namespace studentinfo
{
    public partial class Form3 : Form
    {

        SqlConnection con;
        SqlCommand com;
        string pcell;
        string scell;
        string usn;
        public Form3()
        {
            InitializeComponent();
        }

        private void label5_Click(object sender, EventArgs e)
        {

        }

        private void dbconnect()

```

```

    {
        con = new SqlConnection("Data Source=.\SQLEXPRESS;AttachDbFilena
        con.Open();

    }
private void Form3_Load(object sender, EventArgs e)
{
    textBox3.Text = "0";//for SUBJECT1
    textBox4.Text = "0";//for SUBJECT2
    textBox5.Text = "0";//for SUBJECT3
    textBox6.Text = "0";//for SUBJECT4
    textBox7.Text = "0";//for SUBJECT5
    textBox8.Text = "0";//for SUBJECT6
    gridload();
}
//to fetch the data like USN NAME BRANCH and SEMESTER to display in t
private void gridload()
{
    dbconnect();
    string sql;
    sql = "select * from tbl_student";
    com = new SqlCommand(sql, con);
    SqlDataReader rs = com.ExecuteReader();
    if (rs.HasRows)
    {
        while (rs.Read())
        {
            ListViewItem lv = listView1.Items.Add(rs.GetValue(0).ToSt
            lv.SubItems.Add(rs.GetValue(1).ToString());
            lv.SubItems.Add(rs.GetValue(2).ToString());
            lv.SubItems.Add(rs.GetValue(3).ToString());

        }
    }
    con.Close();
}
//block which takes the inputs like IA NO., IA marks of 6 Subjects
private void button1_Click(object sender, EventArgs e)
{
    dbconnect();
    string sql;
    sql = "insert into iamarks values('" + usn + "',''" + comboBox1.Te
    com = new SqlCommand(sql, con);
    com.ExecuteNonQuery();
    MessageBox.Show("Records updated");

    con.Close();
}
//after each entry the input accept boxes are cleared
private void cleartext()

```

```
{
    textBox3.Text = "0";
    textBox4.Text = "0";
    textBox5.Text = "0";
    textBox6.Text = "0";
    textBox7.Text = "0";
    textBox8.Text = "0";
    comboBox1.Text = "";
}

//block of code to send the IA marks of each student to the respectiv

private void listView1_SelectedIndexChanged(object sender, EventArgs
{
    cleartext();
    dbconnect();
    string sql;
    sql = "select * from tbl_student where usn='" + listView1.Focused
com=new SqlCommand(sql,con);
    SqlDataReader rs = com.ExecuteReader();
    rs.Read();
    usn = rs.GetValue(0).ToString();
    pcell = rs.GetValue(4).ToString();
    scell = rs.GetValue(5).ToString();
    con.Close();
}

private void textBox3_TextChanged(object sender, EventArgs e)
{
}

private void textBox4_TextChanged(object sender, EventArgs e)
{
}

private void button2_Click(object sender, EventArgs e)
{
    this.Hide();
}

private void comboBox1_SelectedIndexChanged(object sender, EventArgs
{
}
}
}
```

A.5 Form4:Code for IA SMS Form

```

using System;
using System.Collections.Generic;
using System.ComponentModel;
using System.Data;
using System.Drawing;
using System.Linq;
using System.Text;
using System.Windows.Forms;
using System.IO.Ports;
using System.Threading;
using System.IO;
using System.Data.SqlClient;
namespace studentinfo
{
    public partial class Form4 : Form
    {
        public SerialPort smsport;
        public string Sread, Swrite;
        SqlConnection con;
        SqlCommand com;
        int cnt = 0;
        //defining an array to fetch the data(USN, SUB1 to SUB6, PARENT MOB N
        string[] arr = new string[30];
        string[] arr1 = new string[30];
        string[] arr2 = new string[30];
        string[] arr3 = new string[30];
        string[] arr4 = new string[30];
        string[] arr5 = new string[30];
        string[] arr6 = new string[30];
        string[] arr7 = new string[10];

        public Form4()
        {
            InitializeComponent();
        }
        //block of code to select the appropriate IA interval to be send
        private void comboBox1_SelectedIndexChanged(object sender, EventArgs
        {
            string s = comboBox1.Text;
            smsport = new SerialPort(s);
            try
            {
                //GSM INITIALIZATION //
                for ( ; ; )
                {

```

```

        Thread.Sleep(1000);
        if (smsport.IsOpen)
        {
            smsport.Close();
        }
        smsport.Open();
        Swrite = "";
        Swrite = "AT\r\n";//checking whether the GSM is properly
        smsport.WriteLine(Swrite);
        smsport.WriteTimeout = 100;
        smsport.ReadTimeout = 100;
        Thread.Sleep(1000);
        Sread = smsport.ReadExisting();
        if (Sread.EndsWith("OK\r\n"))
        {
            bool modem = true;
            Sread = "";
            if (modem == true)
            {
                smscheck(smsport);
                break;
            }
            Console.WriteLine("modem workinG...");
        }
    }
}
catch (Exception ex)
{
    Console.WriteLine("some.." + ex);
}

}

private void Form4_Load(object sender, EventArgs e)
{
}

private void smscheck(SerialPort smsport)
{
    try
    {
        for (; ; )
        {
            Thread.Sleep(1000);
            if (smsport.IsOpen)
            {
                smsport.Close();
            }
            smsport.Open();
        }
    }
}

```

```

        Swrite = "";
        Swrite = "AT+CPIN?\r\n"; // checking whether the SIM is pr
        smsport.WriteLine(Swrite);
        smsport.ReadTimeout = 100;
        Thread.Sleep(1000);
        Sread = smsport.ReadExisting();
        if (Sread.EndsWith("+CPIN: READY\r\n\r\nOK\r\n"))
        {
            bool bsim = true;
            if (bsim == true)
            {
                smstext(smsport);
                break;
            }
        }
    }
}
catch (Exception ex)
{
    Console.WriteLine(ex);
}
}

private void smstext(SerialPort smsport)
{
    string read, write;
    try
    {
        Thread.Sleep(1000);
        if (smsport.IsOpen)
        {
            smsport.Close();
        }
        smsport.Open();
        for (; ; )
        {
            write = "";
            write = "AT+CMGF=1\r\n"; //SMS MODE is set
            smsport.WriteLine(write);
            smsport.WriteTimeout = 100;
            smsport.ReadTimeout = 100;
            Thread.Sleep(1000);
            read = smsport.ReadExisting();
            if (read.EndsWith("OK\r\n"))
            {
                smsreg(smsport);
                break;
            }
        }
    }
}

```

```
    }
    catch (Exception ex)
    {
        Console.WriteLine(ex);
    }
}

private void smsreg(SerialPort smsport)
{
    string read, write;
    try
    {
        for (; ; )
        {
            if (smsport.IsOpen)
            {
                smsport.Close();
            }
            smsport.Open();
            write = "";
            write = "AT+CREG?\r\n"; //check whether the network registr
            smsport.WriteLine(write);
            Thread.Sleep(1000);
            smsport.ReadTimeout = 100;
            read = smsport.ReadExisting();
            if (read.EndsWith("+CREG: 0,5\r\n\r\nOK\r\n") || read.End
            {

                del(smsport);
                break;
            }
        }
    }
    catch (Exception ex)
    {
        MessageBox.Show(ex.Message);
    }
}

private void del(SerialPort smsport)
{
    string read, write;
    try
    {

        if (smsport.IsOpen)
        {
            smsport.Close();
        }
        smsport.Open();
    }
}
```

```

        for ( ; ; )
        {
            write = "";
            write = "AT+CMGDA=" + "'" + "DEL ALL" + "'" + "\r\n";//to
            smsport.WriteLine(write);
            Thread.Sleep(10000);
            smsport.ReadTimeout = 100;
            read = "";
            read = smsport.ReadExisting();
            if (read.EndsWith("OK\r\n"))
            {
                MessageBox.Show("DELETED ALL MESSAGES READY TO READ")
                break;
            }
        }
    }
    catch (Exception ex)
    {
        MessageBox.Show(ex.Message);
    }
}

private void sim_index3(SerialPort smsport)
{
    try
    {
        if (smsport.IsOpen)
        {
            smsport.Close();
        }

        smsport.Open();
        Swrite = "AT+CMGR=3\r\n";//block to store the fetched data in

        smsport.ReadTimeout = 100;
        Thread.Sleep(1000);
        smsport.Write(Swrite);
        Thread.Sleep(1000);
        smsport.WriteTimeout = 1000;
        Sread = "";
        Sread = smsport.ReadExisting();
        if (!Sread.EndsWith("ERROR\r\n"))
        {
            if (Sread.Contains("CARD"))
            {
                int v = Sread.IndexOf("CARD");
                string v1 = Sread.Substring(v, 14);
                string[] v2 = v1.Split('D');
                delete_index3(smsport);
            }
        }
    }
}

```

```
        }
    }
}
catch (Exception ex)
{
    MessageBox.Show(ex.Message);
}
}

private void delete_index3(SerialPort smsport)
{
    try
    {
        if (smsport.IsOpen)
        {
            smsport.Close();
        }
        smsport.Open();
        Thread.Sleep(1000);
        Swrite = "AT+CMGD=3\r\n";
        smsport.ReadTimeout = 1000;
        Thread.Sleep(1000);
        smsport.Write(Swrite);
        smsport.WriteTimeout = 1000;
        Sread = "";
        Thread.Sleep(1000);
        Sread = smsport.ReadExisting();
        if (Sread.EndsWith("OK\r\n"))
        {
        }
    }
}
catch (Exception ex)
{
    MessageBox.Show(ex.Message);
}
finally
{
    smsport.Close();
}
}
```

```
private void sim_index2(SerialPort smsport)
{
    try
    {
        if (smsport.IsOpen)
        {
            smsport.Close();
        }

        smsport.Open();
        Swrite = "AT+CMGR=2\r\n"; //block to store the fetched data in

        smsport.ReadTimeout = 100;
        Thread.Sleep(1000);
        smsport.Write(Swrite);
        Thread.Sleep(1000);
        smsport.WriteTimeout = 1000;
        Sread = "";
        Sread = smsport.ReadExisting();
        if (!Sread.EndsWith("ERROR\r\n"))
        {
            if (Sread.Contains("CARD"))
            {
                int v = Sread.IndexOf("CARD");
                string v1 = Sread.Substring(v, 14);
                string[] v2 = v1.Split('D');

                delete_index3(smsport);
            }
        }
    }
    catch (Exception ex)
    {
        MessageBox.Show(ex.Message);
    }
}

private void delete_index2(SerialPort smsport)
{
    try
    {
        if (smsport.IsOpen)
        {
            smsport.Close();
        }
    }
}
```

```

    }
    smsport.Open();
    Thread.Sleep(1000);
    Swrite = "AT+CMGD=2\r\n";
    smsport.ReadTimeout = 1000;
    Thread.Sleep(1000);
    smsport.Write(Swrite);
    smsport.WriteTimeout = 1000;
    Sread = "";
    Thread.Sleep(1000);
    Sread = smsport.ReadExisting();
    if (Sread.EndsWith("OK\r\n"))
    {
    }
}

}
catch (Exception ex)
{
    MessageBox.Show(ex.Message);
}
finally
{
    smsport.Close();
}
}

private void sim_index1(SerialPort smsport)
{

    try
    {
        if (smsport.IsOpen)
        {
            smsport.Close();
        }

        smsport.Open();
        Swrite = "AT+CMGR=1\r\n";//block to store the fetched data in

        smsport.ReadTimeout = 100;
        Thread.Sleep(1000);
        smsport.Write(Swrite);
        Thread.Sleep(1000);
        smsport.WriteTimeout = 1000;
        Sread = "";
        Sread = smsport.ReadExisting();
        if (!Sread.EndsWith("ERROR\r\n"))
        {
            if (Sread.Contains("CARD"))

```

```
        {
            int v = Sread.IndexOf("CARD");
            string v1 = Sread.Substring(v, 14);
            string[] v2 = v1.Split('D');

            delete_index3(smsport);
        }
    }
}
catch (Exception ex)
{
    MessageBox.Show(ex.Message);
}
}

private void delete_index1(SerialPort smsport)
{
    try
    {
        if (smsport.IsOpen)
        {
            smsport.Close();
        }
        smsport.Open();
        Thread.Sleep(1000);
        Swrite = "AT+CMGD=1\r\n";
        smsport.ReadTimeout = 1000;
        Thread.Sleep(1000);
        smsport.Write(Swrite);
        smsport.WriteTimeout = 1000;
        Sread = "";
        Thread.Sleep(1000);
        Sread = smsport.ReadExisting();
        if (Sread.EndsWith("OK\r\n"))
        {
        }
    }
}
catch (Exception ex)
{
    MessageBox.Show(ex.Message);
}
finally
{
    smsport.Close();
}
```

```

}

private void button2_Click(object sender, EventArgs e)
{
    // block of code to send the SMS to respective parent mob no//
    for (int j = 0; j <$ cnt; j++)
    {
        try
        {
            string write;
            if (smsport.IsOpen)
            {
                smsport.Close();
            }
            smsport.Open();
            write = "";
            write = "AT+CMGS=" + "'" + "+91" + arr[j] + "'" + "\r";

            Thread.Sleep(500);
            smsport.WriteLine(write);
            smsport.WriteTimeout = 10000;
            smsport.ReadTimeout = 100;

            write = "";
            write = "IA: " + arr7[j].ToString() + " SUB1= " + arr1[j]

            Thread.Sleep(500);
            smsport.WriteLine(write);
            smsport.WriteTimeout = 10000;
            smsport.ReadTimeout = 100;
            write = "^z";
            smsport.WriteLine(write);
            MessageBox.Show("MESSAGE SENT ..... CLICK TO CONTINUE FO
            for (int k = 0; k <$= 500; k++) ; //Delay

            for (int m = 0; m <$= 400; m++) ;//Delay

            //timer1.Start();
        }
        catch (Exception ex)
        {
            MessageBox.Show(ex.Message);
        }
        finally
        {
            smsport.Close();
        }
    }
}

```

```

    }

private void timer1_Tick(object sender, EventArgs e)
{
    sim_index1(smsport);
    sim_index2(smsport);
    sim_index3(smsport);
}

private void button1_Click(object sender, EventArgs e)
{
    grid();
}

private void dbconnect()
{
    con = new SqlConnection("Data Source=.\SQLEXPRESS;AttachDbFileName
con.Open();

}

private void grid()
{
    int i = 0;
    listView1.Items.Clear();
    dbconnect();
    string sql;
    sql = "select * from iamarks WHERE IAO='"+comboBox2.Text+"'";
    com = new SqlCommand(sql, con);
    SqlDataReader rs = com.ExecuteReader();
    if (rs.HasRows)
    {
        while (rs.Read())
        {
            ListViewItem lv = listView1.Items.Add(rs.GetValue(0).ToString());
            lv.SubItems.Add(rs.GetValue(1).ToString());
            lv.SubItems.Add(rs.GetValue(2).ToString());
            lv.SubItems.Add(rs.GetValue(3).ToString());
            lv.SubItems.Add(rs.GetValue(4).ToString());
            lv.SubItems.Add(rs.GetValue(5).ToString());
            lv.SubItems.Add(rs.GetValue(6).ToString());
            lv.SubItems.Add(rs.GetValue(7).ToString());
            lv.SubItems.Add(rs.GetValue(8).ToString());
            arr[i] = rs.GetValue(8).ToString();
            arr1[i] = rs.GetValue(2).ToString();
            arr2[i] = rs.GetValue(3).ToString();
            arr3[i] = rs.GetValue(4).ToString();
            arr4[i] = rs.GetValue(5).ToString();
            arr5[i] = rs.GetValue(6).ToString();
            arr6[i] = rs.GetValue(7).ToString();
            arr7[i] = rs.GetValue(1).ToString();
        }
    }
}

```

```
                i++;
                cnt++;
            }

        }
        con.Close();

    }

    private void button3_Click(object sender, EventArgs e)
    {
        this.Hide();
    }

    private void listView1_SelectedIndexChanged(object sender, EventArgs
    {

    }

}
}
```

A.6 Form6:Code for Attendance Entry

```
using System;
using System.Collections.Generic;
using System.ComponentModel;
using System.Data;
using System.Drawing;
using System.Linq;
using System.Text;
using System.Windows.Forms;
using System.Data.SqlClient;
namespace studentinfo
{
    public partial class Form6 : Form
    {
        SqlConnection con;
        SqlCommand com;
```

```
string pcell;
string scell;
string usn;
int mid;
public Form6()
{
    InitializeComponent();
}

private void Form6_Load(object sender, EventArgs e)
{
    mid = 0;

    gridload();
}
private void gridload()
{
    dbconnect();
    string sql;
    sql = "select * from tbl_student";
    com = new SqlCommand(sql, con);
    SqlDataReader rs = com.ExecuteReader();
    if (rs.HasRows)
    {
        while (rs.Read())
        {
            ListViewItem lv = listView1.Items.Add(rs.GetValue(0).ToString());
            lv.SubItems.Add(rs.GetValue(1).ToString());
            lv.SubItems.Add(rs.GetValue(2).ToString());
            lv.SubItems.Add(rs.GetValue(3).ToString());

        }
    }
    con.Close();
}
private void cleartext()
{
    textBox1.Clear();
    textBox2.Clear();
    textBox3.Clear();
    textBox4.Clear();
    textBox5.Clear();
    textBox6.Clear();
    textBox7.Clear();
    textBox8.Clear();
    textBox9.Clear();
    textBox10.Clear();
    textBox11.Clear();
    textBox12.Clear();
    textBox13.Clear();
}
```

```

        textBox14.Clear();
        textBox15.Clear();
        textBox16.Clear();
        textBox17.Clear();
        textBox18.Clear();
        comboBox1.Text = "";
    }

private void listView1_SelectedIndexChanged(object sender, EventArgs
{
    cleartext();
    dbconnect();
    string sql;
    sql = "select * from tbl_student where usn='" + listView1.Focused
com = new SqlCommand(sql, con);
SqlDataReader rs = com.ExecuteReader();
rs.Read();
usn = rs.GetValue(0).ToString();
pcell = rs.GetValue(4).ToString();
scell = rs.GetValue(5).ToString();
con.Close();
}

private void dbconnect()
{
    con = new SqlConnection("Data Source=.\SQLEXPRESS;AttachDbFilena
con.Open();
}

private void button1_Click(object sender, EventArgs e)
{
    idinc();
    dbconnect();

    string sql;
    sql = "insert into tbl_attend values(" + mid + "','" + comboBox1.T
com = new SqlCommand(sql, con);
com.ExecuteNonQuery();
MessageBox.Show("Records updated");

    con.Close();
}

private void idinc()
{
    dbconnect();
    string sql;
    sql = "select max(tid) from tbl_attend";

```

```
com = new SqlCommand(sql, con);
SqlDataReader rs = com.ExecuteReader();
if (rs.HasRows)
{
    rs.Read();
    mid = Convert.ToInt16(rs.GetValue(0));
    mid++;
}

con.Close();
}
private void textBox12_TextChanged(object sender, EventArgs e)
{
    try
    {
        textBox18.Text = ((Convert.ToDouble(textBox12.Text) /

    }
    catch (Exception i)
    {
        MessageBox.Show(i.ToString());
    }
}

private void textBox11_TextChanged(object sender, EventArgs e)
{
    try
    {
        textBox17.Text = ((Convert.ToDouble(textBox11.Text) / Convert.ToD
    }
    catch (Exception i)
    {
        MessageBox.Show(i.ToString());
    }
}

private void textBox2_TextChanged(object sender, EventArgs e)
{
    try
    {
        textBox14.Text = ((Convert.ToDouble(textBox2.Text) / Convert.ToDo
    }
    catch (Exception i)
    {
        MessageBox.Show(i.ToString());
    }
}
```

```
    }
}

private void textBox9_TextChanged(object sender, EventArgs e)
{
    try
    {
        textBox15.Text = ((Convert.ToDouble(textBox9.Text) / Convert.ToDo
        }
    catch (Exception i)
    {
        MessageBox.Show(i.ToString());
    }
}

private void textBox10_TextChanged(object sender, EventArgs e)
{
    try
    {
        textBox16.Text = ((Convert.ToDouble(textBox10.Text) / Convert.ToD
        }
    catch (Exception i)
    {
        MessageBox.Show(i.ToString());
    }
}

private void textBox1_TextChanged(object sender, EventArgs e)
{
    try
    {
        textBox13.Text = ((Convert.ToDouble(textBox1.Text) / Convert.ToD
        }
    catch (Exception i)
    {
        MessageBox.Show(i.ToString());
    }
}

private void button3_Click(object sender, EventArgs e)
{
    cleartext();
    mid = 0;
}
```

```

private void button2_Click(object sender, EventArgs e)
{
    this.Hide();
}

private void textBox18_TextChanged(object sender, EventArgs e)
{
}

private void comboBox1_SelectedIndexChanged(object sender, EventArgs
{
}
}
}

```

A.7 Form7:Code for Attendance SMS

```

using System;
using System.Collections.Generic;
using System.ComponentModel;
using System.Data;
using System.Drawing;
using System.Linq;
using System.Text;
using System.Windows.Forms;
using System.Data.SqlClient;
using System.IO;
using System.Threading;
using System.IO.Ports;
namespace studentinfo
{
    public partial class Form7 : Form
    {
        public SerialPort smsport;
        public string Sread, Swrite;
        SqlConnection con;
        SqlCommand com;
        string ashort = " ";
        int cnt = 0;
        //defining an array to fetch the data(USN, SUB1 to SUB6, PARENT MOB N
        string[] arr = new string[30];
    }
}

```

```
string[] arr1 = new string[30];
string[] arr2 = new string[30];
string[] arr3 = new string[30];
string[] arr4 = new string[30];
string[] arr5 = new string[30];
string[] arr6 = new string[30];
string[] arr7 = new string[10];
string[] arr8 = new string[20];

public Form7()
{
    InitializeComponent();
}

private void Form7_Load(object sender, EventArgs e)
{
    // TODO: This line of code loads data into the 'sisDataSet.tbl_at
    //this.tbl_attendTableAdapter.Fill(this.sisDataSet.tbl_attend);
}

private void dbconnect()
{
    con = new SqlConnection("Data Source=.\SQLEXPRESS;AttachDbFilena
    con.Open();
}

private void grid()
{
    int i = 0;
    listView1.Items.Clear();
    dbconnect();
    string sql;
    sql = "select * from tbl_attend WHERE IANO='" + comboBox2.Text +
    com = new SqlCommand(sql, con);
    SqlDataReader rs = com.ExecuteReader();
    if (rs.HasRows)
    {
        while (rs.Read())
        {
            ListViewItem lv = listView1.Items.Add(rs.GetValue(2).ToSt
            lv.SubItems.Add(rs.GetValue(1).ToString());
            lv.SubItems.Add(rs.GetValue(7).ToString());
            lv.SubItems.Add(rs.GetValue(10).ToString());
            lv.SubItems.Add(rs.GetValue(13).ToString());
            lv.SubItems.Add(rs.GetValue(16).ToString());
            lv.SubItems.Add(rs.GetValue(19).ToString());
            lv.SubItems.Add(rs.GetValue(22).ToString());
            lv.SubItems.Add(rs.GetValue(3).ToString());
        }
    }
}
```

```

arr[i] = rs.GetValue(3).ToString();
arr1[i] = rs.GetValue(1).ToString();
arr2[i] = rs.GetValue(7).ToString();
arr3[i] = rs.GetValue(13).ToString();
arr4[i] = rs.GetValue(16).ToString();
arr5[i] = rs.GetValue(19).ToString();
arr6[i] = rs.GetValue(22).ToString();
arr7[i] = rs.GetValue(2).ToString();
if (Convert.ToDouble(rs.GetValue(7)) <= 75 || Convert.To
    ashort = "SHORTAGE";
else
    ashort = " ";
arr8[i] = ashort.ToString();
lv.SubItems.Add(ashort.ToString());
i++;
cnt++;
    }

}

con.Close();

}

private void button1_Click(object sender, EventArgs e)
{
    grid();
}

private void smscheck(SerialPort smsport)
{
    try
    {
        for (; ; )
        {
            Thread.Sleep(1000);
            if (smsport.IsOpen)
            {
                smsport.Close();
            }
            smsport.Open();
            Swrite = "";
            Swrite = "AT+CPIN?\r\n";// SIM initialization
            smsport.WriteLine(Swrite);
            smsport.ReadTimeout = 100;
            Thread.Sleep(1000);
        }
    }
}

```

```
Sread = smsport.ReadExisting();
if (Sread.EndsWith("+CPIN: READY\r\n\r\nOK\r\n"))
{
    bool bsim = true;
    if (bsim == true)
    {
        smstext(smsport);
        break;
    }
}
}
catch (Exception ex)
{
    Console.WriteLine(ex);
}
}

private void smstext(SerialPort smsport)
{
    string read, write;
    try
    {
        Thread.Sleep(1000);
        if (smsport.IsOpen)
        {
            smsport.Close();
        }
        smsport.Open();
        for (; ; )
        {
            write = "";
            write = "AT+CMGF=1\r\n"; //SMS MODE
            smsport.WriteLine(write);
            smsport.WriteTimeout = 100;
            smsport.ReadTimeout = 100;
            Thread.Sleep(1000);
            read = smsport.ReadExisting();
            if (read.EndsWith("OK\r\n"))
            {
                smsreg(smsport);
                break;
            }
        }
    }
    catch (Exception ex)
    {
        Console.WriteLine(ex);
    }
}
```

```

}

private void smsreg(SerialPort smsport)
{
    string read, write;
    try
    {
        for ( ; ; )
        {
            if (smsport.IsOpen)
            {
                smsport.Close();
            }
            smsport.Open();
            write = "";
            write = "AT+CREG?\r\n";//netwok registration
            smsport.WriteLine(write);
            Thread.Sleep(1000);
            smsport.ReadTimeout = 100;
            read = smsport.ReadExisting();
            if (read.EndsWith("+CREG: 0,5\r\n\r\nOK\r\n") || read.End
            {

                del(smsport);
                break;
            }
        }
    }
    catch (Exception ex)
    {
        MessageBox.Show(ex.Message);
    }
}

private void del(SerialPort smsport)
{
    string read, write;
    try
    {

        if (smsport.IsOpen)
        {
            smsport.Close();
        }
        smsport.Open();
        for ( ; ; )
        {
            write = "";
            write = "AT+CMGDA=" + "'" + "DEL ALL" + "'" + "\r\n";//to
            smsport.WriteLine(write);

```

```

        Thread.Sleep(10000);
        smsport.ReadTimeout = 100;
        read = "";
        read = smsport.ReadExisting();
        if (read.EndsWith("OK\r\n"))
        {
            MessageBox.Show("DELETED ALL MESSAGES READY TO READ");
            break;
        }
    }
}
catch (Exception ex)
{
    MessageBox.Show(ex.Message);
}
}

private void sim_index3(SerialPort smsport)
{
    try
    {
        if (smsport.IsOpen)
        {
            smsport.Close();
        }

        smsport.Open();
        Swrite = "AT+CMGR=3\r\n"; //block to store the fetched data in

        smsport.ReadTimeout = 100;
        Thread.Sleep(1000);
        smsport.Write(Swrite);
        Thread.Sleep(1000);
        smsport.WriteTimeout = 1000;
        Sread = "";
        Sread = smsport.ReadExisting();
        if (!Sread.EndsWith("ERROR\r\n"))
        {
            if (Sread.Contains("CARD"))
            {
                int v = Sread.IndexOf("CARD");
                string v1 = Sread.Substring(v, 14);
                string[] v2 = v1.Split('D');
                delete_index3(smsport);
            }
        }
    }
}
catch (Exception ex)

```

```
    {
        MessageBox.Show(ex.Message);
    }
}

private void delete_index3(SerialPort smsport)
{
    try
    {
        if (smsport.IsOpen)
        {
            smsport.Close();
        }
        smsport.Open();
        Thread.Sleep(1000);
        Swrite = "AT+CMGD=3\r\n";
        smsport.ReadTimeout = 1000;
        Thread.Sleep(1000);
        smsport.Write(Swrite);
        smsport.WriteTimeout = 1000;
        Sread = "";
        Thread.Sleep(1000);
        Sread = smsport.ReadExisting();
        if (Sread.EndsWith("OK\r\n"))
        {
        }
    }
}
catch (Exception ex)
{
    MessageBox.Show(ex.Message);
}
finally
{
    smsport.Close();
}
}

private void sim_index2(SerialPort smsport)
{
```

```

try
{
    if (smsport.IsOpen)
    {
        smsport.Close();
    }

    smsport.Open();
    Swrite = "AT+CMGR=2\r\n"; //block to store the fetched data in

    smsport.ReadTimeout = 100;
    Thread.Sleep(1000);
    smsport.Write(Swrite);
    Thread.Sleep(1000);
    smsport.WriteTimeout = 1000;
    Sread = "";
    Sread = smsport.ReadExisting();
    if (!Sread.EndsWith("ERROR\r\n"))
    {
        if (Sread.Contains("CARD"))
        {
            int v = Sread.IndexOf("CARD");
            string v1 = Sread.Substring(v, 14);
            string[] v2 = v1.Split('D');

            delete_index3(smsport);
        }
    }
}
catch (Exception ex)
{
    MessageBox.Show(ex.Message);
}
}

private void delete_index2(SerialPort smsport)
{
    try
    {
        if (smsport.IsOpen)
        {
            smsport.Close();
        }
        smsport.Open();
        Thread.Sleep(1000);
        Swrite = "AT+CMGD=2\r\n";
        smsport.ReadTimeout = 1000;
    }
}

```

```
        Thread.Sleep(1000);
        smsport.Write(Swrite);
        smsport.WriteTimeout = 1000;
        Sread = "";
        Thread.Sleep(1000);
        Sread = smsport.ReadExisting();
        if (Sread.EndsWith("OK\r\n"))
        {
        }
    }
    catch (Exception ex)
    {
        MessageBox.Show(ex.Message);
    }
    finally
    {
        smsport.Close();
    }
}

private void sim_index1(SerialPort smsport)
{
    try
    {
        if (smsport.IsOpen)
        {
            smsport.Close();
        }

        smsport.Open();
        Swrite = "AT+CMGR=1\r\n";//block to store the fetched data in

        smsport.ReadTimeout = 100;
        Thread.Sleep(1000);
        smsport.Write(Swrite);
        Thread.Sleep(1000);
        smsport.WriteTimeout = 1000;
        Sread = "";
        Sread = smsport.ReadExisting();
        if (!Sread.EndsWith("ERROR\r\n"))
        {
            if (Sread.Contains("CARD"))
            {
                int v = Sread.IndexOf("CARD");
                string v1 = Sread.Substring(v, 14);
                string[] v2 = v1.Split('D');
```

```
        delete_index3(smsport);
    }

    }
}
catch (Exception ex)
{
    MessageBox.Show(ex.Message);
}
}

private void delete_index1(SerialPort smsport)
{
    try
    {
        if (smsport.IsOpen)
        {
            smsport.Close();
        }
        smsport.Open();
        Thread.Sleep(1000);
        Swrite = "AT+CMGD=1\r\n";
        smsport.ReadTimeout = 1000;
        Thread.Sleep(1000);
        smsport.Write(Swrite);
        smsport.WriteTimeout = 1000;
        Sread = "";
        Thread.Sleep(1000);
        Sread = smsport.ReadExisting();
        if (Sread.EndsWith("OK\r\n"))
        {
        }

    }

    catch (Exception ex)
    {
        MessageBox.Show(ex.Message);
    }
    finally
    {
        smsport.Close();
    }
}

private void comboBox1_SelectedIndexChanged(object sender, EventArgs
```

```

{
    string s = comboBox1.Text;
    smsport = new SerialPort(s);
    try
    {
        for ( ; ; )
        {
            Thread.Sleep(1000);
            if (smsport.IsOpen)
            {
                smsport.Close();
            }
            smsport.Open(); //initializing the GSM by setting AT cmd
            Swrite = "";
            Swrite = "AT\r\n";
            smsport.WriteLine(Swrite);
            smsport.WriteTimeout = 100;
            smsport.ReadTimeout = 100;
            Thread.Sleep(1000);
            Sread = smsport.ReadExisting();
            if (Sread.EndsWith("OK\r\n"))
            {
                bool modem = true;
                Sread = "";
                if (modem == true)
                {
                    smscheck(smsport);
                    break;
                }
                Console.WriteLine("modem workinG...");
            }
        }
    }
    catch (Exception ex)
    {
        Console.WriteLine("some.." + ex);
    }
}

private void timer1_Tick(object sender, EventArgs e)
{
    sim_index1(smsport);
    sim_index2(smsport);
    sim_index3(smsport);
}

private void button2_Click(object sender, EventArgs e)
{

```

```

for (int j = 0; j <$ cnt; j++)
{
    try
    {
        string write;
        if (smsport.IsOpen)
        {
            smsport.Close();
        }
        smsport.Open();
        write = "";
        write = "AT+CMGS=" + "'" + "+91" + arr[j] + "'" + "\r";//

        Thread.Sleep(500);
        smsport.WriteLine(write);
        smsport.WriteTimeout = 10000;
        smsport.ReadTimeout = 100;

        write = "";
        write = "NUMBER : " + arr7[j].ToString() + " SUB1 $\%$ =

        Thread.Sleep(500);
        smsport.WriteLine(write);
        smsport.WriteTimeout = 10000;
        smsport.ReadTimeout = 100;
        write = "^z";
        smsport.WriteLine(write);
        MessageBox.Show("MESSAGE SENT ..... CLICK TO CONTINUE FO
        for (int k = 0; k <=$= 500; k++) ;

        for (int m = 0; m <=$= 400; m++) ;

        //timer1.Start();
    }
    catch (Exception ex)
    {
        MessageBox.Show(ex.Message);
    }
    finally
    {
        smsport.Close();
    }
}

private void comboBox2_SelectedIndexChanged(object sender, EventArgs
{

```

```
    }  
  
    private void listView1_SelectedIndexChanged(object sender, EventArgs  
    {  
  
    }  
}  
}
```